

DISCRETE LATENT VARIABLE MODELS: ADVANCES IN THE ANALYSIS OF LONGITUDINAL DATA

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Introduction

Latent variable models include unobservable variables to describe the relation between observable variables. Among these models, those based on a latent discrete distribution are nowadays commonly used (for a recent review see Bartolucci et al., 2022). In particular, discrete latent variable (DLV) models present some advantages such as the high degree of flexibility in dealing with complex dependence structures and the capability of clustering units in different latent groups.

The aim of this work is to provide a critical review of DLV models and to illustrate a new possible application of the models to the analysis of temporal compositional data.

Methods

This work is motivated by the availability of a dataset about the annual capital stock wealth amount in $r = 15$ different sectors for the period from 1964 to 2020, corresponding to $T = 56$ years (García et al., 2023). Data are referred to $n = 18$ regions of Spain and, for each region and year, the capital stock wealth amounts across sectors are transformed into compositions (Greenacre, 2021). To analyze these data, a hidden Markov (HM) model is proposed, which is based on a conditional Dirichlet distribution for the compositions given the underlying latent states, where these states follow a first order Markov chain.

Results

The model allows us to cluster the Spanish regions in a dynamic fashion, so that the same region may move between clusters across time. The results of the proposed model, which may be reported in a graphical way, are also

compared with those of a traditional HM model based on the multivariate Gaussian distribution for the log-ratio transformation of the data using a specific reference category.

As a future development we consider a spatio-temporal model where the latent state of a region in a certain year may depend also on the state of the neighboring regions (Bartolucci and Farcomeni, 2022).

References

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